

Impact of Foreign Direct Investment on Economic Growth in Sub-Sahara Africa Countries

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Abstract

This study examines the impact of foreign direct investment on economic growth in Sub-Saharan African countries using a Panel Autoregressive Distributed Lag (P-ARDL) model. We employ this method due to its flexibility in accommodating both stationary and non-stationary time series, as well as series with mixed integration orders, while also allowing for sufficient lags to capture the data's dynamics. The findings indicate that, despite varied short-term impacts, foreign direct investment, human capital, and GDP per capita have substantial long-term effects on economic growth in the region. These findings contribute to the debate on FDI's role in tackling widespread poverty, high unemployment, and inflationary challenges facing Sub-Saharan African countries. The study recommends that policymakers in Sub-Saharan Africa countries should prioritize targeted policies to attract FDI, reform human capital development, and promote job creation, infrastructure growth, and strong institutions to boost per capita income and drive sustainable economic growth.

Keyword: Foreign Direct Investment, Economic Growth, ARDL Model

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1. Introduction

The economic situations across Sub-Saharan African countries exhibit significant disparities, with many of these countries falling below the low-income category (Rodríguez-Pose and Tijmstra, 2007) and exhibiting high rate of poverty and unemployment. According to data from the World Bank in 2025 that highlighted the problem, Western and Central Africa are expected to experience a decline in GDP growth, projected to drop from 3.7% in 2022 to 3.4% in 2027. Likewise, Eastern and Southern Africa are also poised for a GDP growth decrease, anticipated to fall from 3.5% in 2022 to 3% in 2027.

While various studies have pointed out the limited economic dynamism experienced by this region in recent decades, it is evident that the Sub-Saharan African countries grapple with a host of economic challenges. These challenges include widespread poverty, a high level of unemployment, inflationary pressures, weak institutions, climate change, and an imbalanced demographic structure characterized by elevated fertility rates as well as the prevalence of health issues stemming from inadequate investments in the healthcare sector (Ayenew, 2022). These challenges have significant economic implications and, if left unaddressed, could escalate into low growth rates, higher crime rates and destabilize the region. For instance, de Haan (2017) emphasized that rural and urban poverty within the region is closely linked to deprivation and public health challenges which have perpetuate social exclusion, and inequalities, which, in turn, hinder robust economic growth in the sub-Saharan Africa countries.

Specifically, according to the IMF's latest Regional Economic Outlook (IMF, 2025), Sub-Saharan Africa's economic growth is expected to stay subdued at 3.6% in 2024, unchanged from 2023, before edging up to 4.2% in 2025. However, this growth rate is insufficient to drive meaningful poverty reduction, reduce unemployment and tackle pressing development challenges. The region's countries continue to face macroeconomic challenges, constrained financing, and growing social pressures, forcing policymakers to make tough decisions in implementing reforms. Projections suggest that economic growth in the region is anticipated to continue at a slow pace, with projections suggesting a range of 4.1% to 4.3% for 2026-2027 (World Bank, 2025).

Nonetheless, the role of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) has been emphasized in many studies as one of the flows of private capital through globalization (Bekere and Bersisa, 2018) that can support the growth of the region and address the problem of poverty and unemployment as well

as supporting the government to build strong institutions. As a result, this study seeks to examine the impact of foreign direct investment on economic growth for the Sub-Saharan African countries. The importance of FDI as a form of external finance to Sub-Sahara Africa reflects not only the fact that firms increasingly find benefits in expanding their production internationally but also that host developing countries see potential advantages in FDI over other forms of investment like foreign portfolio investment in their economies (Jugurnath et al. 2016), by boosting productivity and reduce unemployment.

In Solow growth model, foreign direct investment (FDI) allows host countries to invest beyond their domestic savings, thereby boosting capital formation (Bekere and Bersisa, 2018). Although, the model suggests that FDI's positive impact on economic growth is limited to the short term. In the long term, due to diminishing returns on capital, the economy may return to its steady-state growth rate, negating FDI's lasting impact. In contrast, endogenous growth models emphasize the role of technology, efficiency, and productivity, suggesting that FDI can sustainably boost growth if it generates increasing returns through externalities and spillovers. Zamani and Tayebi's (2022) findings support this view, revealing that FDI spillovers have a significantly positive impact on economic growth, suggesting long-term sustainability.

Given the above outcomes from endogenous growth models and some other researchers, countries in Sub-Sahara Africa have remain and largely dependent on FDI after a global surge at a point where the inflow of FDI moved from 17% in 1990 to 55% in 2014 (Kargbo, 2017) and over 70% in 2023. According to UNCTAD (2024), “Africa attracted a record US\$97 billion in FDI in 2024, which is a 75% surge compared to the previous year”. Despite the increase in the inflow, the present level of national savings and investment in the region are insufficient to ensure a process of development necessary to place Sub-Sahara Africa on a sustainable path. In light of this, our research aims to reassess the relationship between Foreign Direct Investment and economic growth in Sub-Saharan Africa, providing a fresh examination of this critical relationship.

Following this introduction, the rest of the paper is structured in five sections. Section 2 is a brief review of the literature (theoretical and empirical review) on the impact of foreign direct investment on economic growth in Sub-Saharan African countries. A discussion of the Data and Methodology used is presented in Section 3, followed by an extensive discussion of the study's result in section 4. The study's limitations and areas for improvement is presented in section 5 while a summary and conclusion conclude the paper in Section 6.

2. Literature Review

This section reviews the theoretical and empirical literature on the impact of foreign direct investment on economic growth in Sub-Saharan African countries, providing a foundation for our study. The section is divided as follows:

2.1 The Theoretical Review

The theoretical framework underpinning the relationship between FDI and economic growth incorporates various theoretical perspectives. Key theories include the neoclassical theory, endogenous growth theory, and technology spillover theory. According to the neoclassical economic theory, FDI inflows play a crucial role in advancing economic growth by facilitating the transfer of technology, boosting productivity, and stimulating domestic investment. This means that the neoclassical theory posits that FDI inflows bring capital, technology, and managerial skills, which contribute to economic growth. Woo (2009) and Osano and Koine (2016) rooted their studies from the neoclassical theory and asserted that FDI promotes the diffusion of technology, enhances productivity, and contributes to economic growth. They emphasized that FDI facilitates the accumulation of capital, diffusion of technology, and development of human capital, all of which are integral to sustaining economic growth in the region.

Endogenous growth theory on the other hand suggests that FDI generates spillover effects, leading to technological progress and long-term economic growth. The key aspect of endogenous growth theory is that FDI can bring in new technologies, management practices, and skills, leading to positive spillover effects that can drive long-term economic growth. These spillovers can benefit domestic firms and industries, contributing to increased productivity and innovation.

The technology spillover theory also suggests that FDI leads to knowledge transfer and productivity gains, benefiting the host country's economy. Drawing on the insights from these theoretical frameworks, this study examines the impact of FDI on economic growth in Sub-Saharan Africa, grounded in the principles of these three theories.

2.2 The Review of Empirical Literature

Numerous empirical investigations have extensively examined the relationship between foreign direct investment (FDI) and economic growth in Sub-Saharan Africa, providing valuable insights into this complex association. For example, Asiedu (2002) examined the impact of FDI on economic growth in 30 Sub-Saharan African countries, providing empirical

evidence supporting the positive impact of FDI on productivity and innovation in SSA economies. The study highlighted the role of FDI in improving total factor productivity, thereby contributing to economic growth. Similarly, Okafor (2014) focused on the role of FDI in promoting technological diffusion, further supporting the positive influence of FDI on economic growth in Sub-Saharan African countries. Musibau et al. (2019) also find overwhelming evidence that foreign capital inflows and human development have a significant effect on economic growth in ECOWAS member countries, and that FDI and gross domestic investment are positively related to economic growth in sub-region's economies.

In a study by Kendigelen (2024), the impact of foreign direct investment (FDI) on economic growth in Sub-Saharan Africa was investigated, with a specific emphasis on infrastructure development. The results demonstrated a robust and statistically significant positive correlation between FDI and economic growth in the region. Notably, the study highlighted the critical role of infrastructure development as a conduit through which FDI influences economic growth. This underscores the importance of making significant investments in infrastructure to maximize the advantages of FDI and promote long-term economic development in Sub-Saharan Africa.

In addition, Asongu et al. (2021) investigate the simultaneous openness hypothesis by assessing the importance of trade openness in modulating the effect of foreign direct investment (FDI) on the economic dynamics of gross domestic product (GDP) growth, real GDP, and GDP per capita. The focus of the study was on 25 countries in Sub-Saharan Africa over the period spanning from 1980 to 2014. Based on the findings, trade imports modulate FDI to induce net positive effects on GDP growth and GDP per capita in the region. This finding is similar to Asafo-Agyei (2020) that carry out a study on foreign direct investment and its spillover effects on economic growth in Africa.

Furthermore, Ibhagui (2020) explores the impact of foreign direct investment on growth in sub-Saharan Africa using a threshold analysis approach. The study's findings indicate that FDI promotes economic growth in SSA countries when certain threshold conditions are met, specifically: low inflation, optimal population growth, and developed financial markets. Notably, FDI enhances growth when inflation and private sector credit are below certain thresholds, while human capital and population growth exceed their respective thresholds

On the contrary, Agbloyor et al. (2016) examine the relationship among foreign direct investment (FDI), institutions and economic growth in sub-Saharan Africa region. The study employed a two-step generalized methods of moments estimator with Weidmeijer corrected standard errors and orthogonal deviations to examine the empirical relations. The study did not find evidence that FDI promotes growth.

In addition, Asamoah et al. (2019) used the Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) technique with data from 34 SSA countries covering the period 1996 to 2016 to investigate the role of institutions as an interactive factor in the FDI, trade and growth nexus in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) region. They find evidence of a decreasing effect of FDI on economic growth.

Moreover, Rajab and Zouheir (2024) investigate the complementarity relationship between foreign direct investment, human capital threshold and economic growth in 15 least developed African countries. Employing econometric technique GMM and the regression of the dynamic threshold (TR), the result shows that foreign direct investment and human capital have no significant impact on economic growth.

Furthermore, Adams and Opoku (2015) examine the impact of the regulatory regime, namely, credit market regulations, business regulations, and labour market regulations, on the FDI-growth nexus in 22 sub-Saharan African countries over the period 1980 to 2011. Based on general methods of moments (GMM) estimation approach, they find that FDI does not directly affect economic growth; it affects positively growth when interacted linearly with regulatory regime variables.

Given the divergent perspectives on FDI's impact and its significance on economic growth, this study's empirical investigation into its effects on the SSA region is both timely and crucial.

3. Data Specification and Methodology

This section deals with the methodology used to analyse the data as well as sources of the data. We follow the pattern of Prasad and Espinoza (2012), Ciccarelli et al. (2013) and Davoodi et al. (2013) who carried out a panel analyses on Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) countries, the euro area and East Africa, respectively. The panel analysis or methodology involve pooling cross-sectional data together owing to the distinctive characteristics of the Sub-Saharan African countries' economies, such as: (i) many of the countries have shifted their monetary policy regimes, adopting inflation targeting coupled with a floating exchange rate system (Mallick and Sousa, 2012), (ii) establishment of the Africa's Development Bank to foster greater financial and developmental cooperation among the member countries, and, (iii) Sub-Saharan

African countries are similarly vulnerable to the same external shocks due to the significant influence of the US dollar on their economies, particularly since many of their exports and imports are denominated in US dollars (see Taiwo, 2024).

3.1 Methodology

This study employs the use of Panel Autoregressive Distributed Lag (P-ARDL) model. We employ the panel ARDL model due to its flexibility in handling both stationary and non-stationary time series, as well as series with mixed integration orders, while also allowing for sufficient lags to capture the data's dynamics as highlighted by Chudik and Pesaran (2013). In addition, the model addresses the problem of multicollinearity. This method is to help examine the impact of foreign direct investment on economic growth in Sub-Sahara Africa. The model will further examine the relationship between FDI and economic growth in Sub-Sahara Africa region. The study employs unit root testing using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test and Levin, Lin and Chu (LLC) methods. We employ the two different methods in order to cross-validate and compare results, ensuring consistency and robustness, which is in line with the approaches of Demetriades et al. (2012) and Ishibashi (2012).

3.2 The Model specification for the Panel ARDL

To examine the impact of foreign direct investment and economic growth of sub-Sahara Africa, this study conducted a comprehensive comparative analysis of the Sub-Sahara Africa region. The study employs the model of Ayenew (2022) and specifies Panel ARDL, expressed as follows:

$$\Delta LNRGDP_{it} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 LNRGDP_{it-1} + \beta_2 LNGDPK_{it-1} + \beta_3 FDI_{it-1} + \beta_4 HCI_{it-1} + \sum_{i=1}^p \alpha_1 \Delta LHCI_{it-i} + \sum_{i=1}^p \alpha_2 \Delta LGDPK_{it-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q \alpha_3 \Delta LRGDP_{it-i} + \sum_{i=2}^r \alpha_4 \Delta FDI_{it-i} + \varepsilon_t \dots \dots \dots 1$$

For the equation above, the coefficients $(\beta_1 - \beta_4)$ measure short run relationships; while $(\alpha_1 - \alpha_4)$ capture long run dynamics. In order to get the feedback effect or speed of adjustment of the model when disequilibrium in the short term occurred, the Error Correction Model is expressed as:

$$\Delta LRGDP_t = \zeta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p \alpha_1 \Delta LRGDP_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q \alpha_2 \Delta LGDPK_{t-i} + \sum_{i=2}^r \alpha_3 \Delta LHCI_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q \alpha_4 \Delta FDI_{t-i} + \eta ECT_{t-i} + \mu_t \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

3.3 Data Sources

This study's data is sourced from the World Development Indicators (WDI) and the United Nations Data Portal (UN DATA), covering 39 Sub-Saharan African countries from 1970 to

2024. The selected time period was chosen due to data availability and its relevance to key phases of the continent's development, including economic reforms and global economic downturns. The variables included in the model are Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), GDP per capital (GDPK), Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP) and Human Capital Index (HCI). All these variables are rooted from the theoretical review underpinning the relationship between FDI and economic growth.

4. Result and Discussion

This section presents the results derived from the analysis using the panel ARDL model. It further contains the discussion of the study's results as shown below:

4.1 Unit Root Test Result

Table 1 shows the unit root test results using the ADF and LCC approaches. Based on the results derived from the analysis, none of the variables is in I(2). Both RGDP and GDPK were stationary at first differencing (I(1)) while FDI and HCI were stationary at levels (I(0)). As a result, the condition for using Panel ARDL model is satisfied, in line with the Chudik and Pesaran (2013) P-ARDL model condition for testing and running a panel ARDL model.

Table 1: Unit Root Test Result

Variables	Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF)			Levin, Lin and Chu (LLC)		
	Order of integration	t* Statistics	P-Value	Order of integration	t* Statistics	P-Value
RGDP	I(1)	-7.06046	0.0000***	I(1)	-36.2116	0.0000***
GDPK	I(1)	-1.75217	0.0014***	I(1)	-22.82306	0.0141**
FDI	I(0)	-5.007	0.0000***	I(0)	26.2605	0.0000***
HCI	I(0)	-11.7836	0.0000***	I(0)	-19.2786	0.0000***

“***”, “**” and “*” represent statistical significance at 1%, 5%, and 10% respectively.

4.2 The Panel ARDL Result

Table 2 shows the Panel ARDL short run dynamic estimation result. This analytical approach aimed to illuminate the underlying dynamics that governed economic growth and its distinct determinants within this region. Based on the findings, Lagged Real GDP Output (RGDP (-1)) indicates a robust positive connection between previous real GDP output and the current real GDP output. This suggests a sustained growth pattern, implying that a unit increase in the previous GDP corresponds to a unit rise in current GDP. This finding aligns with Leimbach (2017) that revealed that the GDP projections are put into the context of historic patterns of economic growth based on its corresponding contribution to the current one (GDP). This finding is significant because understanding historical GDP growth trends is crucial for investors, as it

enables them to plan strategically and mitigate potential future risks. Additionally, understanding historical GDP trends can inform policymakers' forecasts of economic activity in Sub-Saharan Africa, enabling more effective decision-making.

In addition, the interplay between GDP per capita (GDPK) was characterized by an insignificant impact both at the current and previous year, indicating its lack of certainty on the validity of stimulating economic growth within the studied countries. Although it exerts a positive relation, it nonetheless showing a weak response in stimulating economic growth in the region. This might not be unconnected with the high rate of poverty and unemployment in the region. This conforms to Gil-Alana et al. (2021) that revealed that the number of people living in absolute poverty in African countries has increased by more than 100 million, hence, leading to low per capita income. The significance of this finding lies in its urgent need by policymakers in Sub-Saharan African countries to develop a framework that will increase investment in human capital, promoting economic growth through implementing policies that foster entrepreneurship, innovation, and investment, and creating a business-friendly environment, reducing bureaucracy, and providing incentives.

Furthermore, the results indicate that foreign direct investment (FDI) has a positive but insignificant impact on economic growth in the current year, suggesting that FDI does not substantially boost growth in the short term. Similarly, the effect of FDI in the previous year is also positive but insignificant. These findings imply that increased FDI inflows will lead to sluggish, rather than rapid, improvements in economic growth in both the current and previous years in the short run. This finding is similar to Adegboye et al. (2020) and Joshua et al. (2021) that FDI is crucial to in stimulating economic growth in the long run.

Table 2: Panel ARDL Short Run Dynamic Estimation Result

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
RGDP	-2.349	2.256	-1.042	0.298
RGDP(-1)	0.946	0.0089	106.77	0.0002***
GDPK	53.161	91.063	0.584	0.551
GDPK(-1)	0.0039	0.0048	0.8235	0.456
FDI	29.243	214.91	0.136	0.892
FDI(-1)	2.275	2.3323	0.975	0.321
HCI	-100722.5	7809.8	-12.81	0.0005***
HCI(-1)	-95957.05	7773.1	-12.34	0.0001***
C	-0.5908	0.0616	-9.59	0.0006

“***”, “**” and “*” represent statistical significance at 1%, 5%, and 10% respectively.

In contrast, the human capital index (HCI) has a significant but negative impact on economic growth in both the current and previous years, highlighting its crucial impact in affecting economic growth in the short term. This finding is in line with Bekele et al. (2024) that found that human capital has a negative and statistically significant impact on economic growth in the SSA region. The result suggests that by tracking the HCI, policymakers and researchers can identify areas for improvement and develop targeted strategies to enhance human capital, ultimately driving economic growth and development in Sub-Saharan Africa region. To achieve this, policymakers in the region should consider overhauling their human capital development framework, prioritizing quality education over mere access to education.

Table 3 on the other hand shows the long run dynamic estimation result. Based on the results derived from the estimated model, GDP per capita, foreign direct investment and human capital demonstrates a strong and significant effect on economic growth. Specifically, both GDP per capita and foreign direct investment exert a strong positive effect on economic growth in the long run. This means that an increase in GDP per capita and foreign direct investment will lead to a simultaneous increase in economic growth in the SSA region. Our finding conforms to Rajab and Zouheir (2024) that found a positive and significant effect of foreign direct investment on economic growth in 15 least developed African countries. It is therefore crucial for SSA policymakers to develop and refine policies that enhance their absorption capacities, enabling them to effectively attract and maximize the benefits of foreign direct investment.

Similarly, human capital has a significant but negative impact on economic growth, consistent with the short-term findings and in line with Ibhagui's (2020) study, which also reported a negative relationship between human capital development and economic growth in in sub-Saharan Africa region. This outcome may be linked to the region's unique challenges, which limit its ability to absorb and effectively utilize human capital, hindering economic transformation and prosperity. As a result, it is important for policymakers to prioritize human capital development, and strengthening institutions, reducing corruption, and improving transparency in order to promote economic growth in the region.

Table 3: Estimated Panel ARDL long run result

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
GDPK	0.717871	0.028637	25.06809	0.0000***
FDI	0.000732	0.000146	5.023498	0.0000***
HCI	-0.000779	0.000152	-5.118115	0.0000***

The result of the diagnostics tests conducted on the Panel ARDL model is shown in Table 4. It contains Normality, Heteroscedasticity and Serial correlation tests. The essence of conducting the diagnostic tests is to ensure the model's assumptions are met, identify potential issues like omitted variables, incorrect functional form, or misspecification, examine residuals for patterns, autocorrelation, or heteroscedasticity, which can affect model reliability, assess the model's fit, accuracy, and robustness as well as identifying and addressing issues, diagnostic tests help increase the model's validity and reliability (see Kumar, 2023). Based on the findings, there is no evidence of heteroscedasticity and serial correlation in the model, and the residuals are normal (normally distributed). This finding conforms to Ceesay and Moussa (2022) that carried out a study titled “Pooled ordinary least-square, fixed effects and random effects modelling in a panel data regression analysis: A consideration of international commodity price and economic growth indicators in 35 Sub-Saharan African countries.” Therefore, the significance of this is that our model is valid, reliable and consistent in analysing the impact of foreign direct investment on economic growth in Sub-Sahara Africa countries.

Table 4: Results for diagnostics tests

Test	t-Statistic	Prob.*	Decision
Normality	1.3789	0.36519	Residuals are normal (normally distributed)
Serial correlation	0.7749	0.1728	No serial correlation
Heteroscedasticity	1.1528	0.6201	No case of heteroskedasticity
Ramsey reset	0.3226	0.1162	Model is well specified

Figure 1: Stability Test

Figure 1 presents the stability test results, which confirm the model's stability at a 5% significance level using the CUSUM test. The parameters of the estimated model (thin blue

line) lie within the 5% critical bounds (red lines), indicating stability of the Panel ARDL model. As a result, it can be validly concluded that the model's parameters remain stable, reliable and the relationships between variables are consistent in line with Kumar (2023). In addition, it can be inferred that there is no structural breaks that can impact the accuracy and reliability of the results. Our model therefore demonstrates strong forecasting capabilities, making it a valuable tool for predicting the effects of foreign direct investment on economic growth in Sub-Saharan Africa region.

5. Limitations and Areas for Further Research

The debate on the impact of foreign direct investment on economic growth is becoming increasingly complicated due to global events and unstable financial structures in the Sub-Saharan African countries. This calls for further research. One of the limitations of this study could be the area of not capturing important variables that may have been included in the panel ARDL model. As a way of addressing this issue, a study can be conducted using the Dynamic Stochastic General Equilibrium model (DSGE), which improves the panel ARDL model and other traditional structural methodologies by including more variables without the risk of running out of degrees of freedom. Finally, the Chudik and Pesaran (2013) P-ARDL model employed in this study could be improved by using the cross-section augmented distributed lag (CS-DL) approach developed by Chudik *et al.* (2015) to model cross-section correlated errors.

6. Conclusion and Policy Recommendation

This study investigates the impact of foreign direct investment (FDI) on economic growth in Sub-Saharan African countries from 1970 to 2024. The results show that FDI inflow has a significant and positive effect on economic growth, suggesting that increased FDI leads to improved economic performance in the long run. This finding aligns with our expectations and supports the trade-led growth hypothesis and FDI-led growth nexus, suggesting that increased FDI can contribute to economic growth in Sub-Saharan African countries. The trade-led growth hypothesis suggests that a country's economic growth is driven by its level of international trade, particularly exports. It proposes that increased trade openness and export-oriented policies can lead to economic growth by increasing foreign exchange earnings, improving productivity and competitiveness, attracting foreign direct investment and encouraging specialization and efficiency (Sakyi et al., 2015). Given FDI's significant long-term benefits for Sub-Saharan African economies, policymakers should develop targeted policies to attract foreign direct investment, fostering job creation, build strong institutions, infrastructure development, and technology transfer to drive sustainable economic growth.

Additionally, while GDP per capita exerts a strong positive impact on economic growth in the region, human capital development on the other hand exerts a strong negative impact on the economy. Our results suggest that higher per capita income will be associated with increased economic growth, consistent with the findings of Albiman and Sulong (2016) while human capital contributed negatively to economic growth, with significant indicators pointing to a declining trend. This finding underscores the critical role of human capital in driving long-term economic growth, emphasizing the need for policymakers and researchers to pinpoint areas for improvement and craft targeted strategies enhancing human capital through targeted initiatives to promote economic development in Sub-Saharan Africa. A key policy recommendation is for regional policymakers to overhaul their human capital development approach, shifting emphasis from mere access to education to ensuring quality education that drives economic growth.

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